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The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to the Scottish Parliament's call for views in advance of the draft Climate Change Plan

This document provides a response to the Scottish Parliament's [call for views on the anticipated Climate Change Plan for 2026-2040](#). This submission addresses the policies, challenges, and opportunities for the land use and agriculture sectors in meeting Scotland's ambitious climate targets, with a central focus on ensuring a just transition. Scotland's statutory climate targets are heavily reliant on these sectors, including through peatland restoration on agricultural land. However, achieving climate goals in a fair and equitable manner requires a fundamental shift from the current fragmented and market-driven approach to a more integrated, strategic, and just governance framework. Current policies, while laudable in their aims and ambitions, risk exacerbating existing inequalities relating to the ownership and control of natural resources, potentially disempowering smaller farmers, crofters, tenants, and rural communities. A successful and just Climate Change Plan (CCP) must move beyond hectare-based targets to a holistic approach that integrates climate action with agricultural policy, nature restoration, community wealth building, and land reform.

LAND USE, LAND USE CHANGE, AND FORESTRY (LULUCF) SECTOR

1. What are the most important policies needed to achieve the proposed carbon budgets level for 2026-40 in this sector?

That forestry and peatlands are the two key pillars of the LULUCF sector in Scotland is explicitly recognised in the current Climate Change Plan (updated 2020). The [Climate Change Committee](#) has also considered that Scotland's Third and Fourth Carbon Budgets are heavily reliant on the agriculture and land use sectors, including by offsetting remaining emissions from livestock through afforestation and peatland restoration.

The current quantitative target to restore 250,000 hectares of degraded peatland by 2030 is the most concrete national target relating to peatlands in Scotland, and, therefore, a key driver of policy change. Yet, progress towards meeting Scotland's aspirations for climate change mitigation through peatland restoration has been slow and, particularly in relation to agricultural peatlands, requires more than a simple, area-based approach.

The most important policies needed are:

- **A more integrated and strategic approach** to land use and land use change, to deliver ambitious climate change targets. Peatlands sit within a very fragmented area of law- and policymaking. This does not only lead to a **lack of clarity** and conflict at strategic level – e.g., between policy objectives on climate and nature, and on agricultural production – but at the implementation stage – e.g., between different pots of public funding, for peatland restoration and for agriculture. Much stronger links are needed between a new Climate Change Plan and the Fourth Land Use Strategy (under the Climate Change Act 2009) and other key laws and policies such as the Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Act 2024, the Land Reform Bill (and mandatory public Land Management Plans thereunder), the Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital and the Draft Just Transition Plan for the agriculture and land use sectors. The Fourth Land Use Strategy should be at the centre of action across cross-sectoral and sectoral policies and requires better political and financial support to provide clear direction on managing trade-offs on the path towards net zero.
- **A shift towards outcome-based public funding**, including [Peatland ACTION funding](#). Allocating funds on the basis of clearly defined, transparent outcomes rather than hectare counts will contribute to a more effective targeting of public funds to deliver on multiple policy objectives. A focus on carbon often prioritises large-scale projects with simple governance structures (e.g., single owners) which can exacerbate existing inequalities in the way decisions about land are made and benefits are distributed. It is also noted that even from a carbon point of view this can be ineffective, as potential sequestration varies across hectares and at different points in time, and future benefits may not be realised due to the temporal and spatial developments of landscapes, e.g., local heating due to climate change. A shift in approach could refocus funding decisions on achieving multiple objectives/providing multiple benefits such as relating to climate change mitigation *and* adaptation, biodiversity, water, community wealth building and a just transition, as well as potential benefits from and for the historic environment.
- **Robust regulation of private finance and natural capital markets.** The current approach to realising land use change – such as the restoration and sustainable management of peatlands - for climate targets, relies heavily on voluntary action by farmers and landowners, shaped by unregulated market dynamics. This is insufficient to guarantee public goods and a just transition. Policies are needed to [regulate voluntary carbon and nature markets](#) to ensure projects deliver genuine, lasting climate, ecological and social benefits and do not simply serve as a mechanism for ‘moving money around’. This includes establishing clear legal responsibilities and liabilities for project delivery, especially in complex collaborations which require the setting up of new companies.
- **Development of new mechanisms for the adaptive governance of a just transition towards net zero.** Such mechanisms must make land use (decisions) more inclusive of public and community voices, ensuring fairer distribution of benefits from land use change for current and future generations. In this regard, the piloted Regional Land Use Partnerships – and the South of Scotland Regional Land Use Framework – deserve much more attention and must be considered as entities capable of distributing funding, in accordance with previous advice from the [Scottish Land Commission](#) (2020).
- **Investment in data, as well as robust monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV).** Access to data, particularly research data including (pre)historic environmental data from historical research, must be improved and funding needs to be made available to maintain data sets upon completion of research. Furthermore, the effectiveness and credibility of restoration projects, particularly where there is reliance on private finance, is reliant on robust (and publicly funded) mechanisms for monitoring, reporting and verification of benefits. International research in relation to nature markets shows that where MRV is lacking, this often results in limited tangible environmental gains/outcomes.¹

2. When should these policies be introduced, and over what timeframe should they be implemented?

The urgency of action is reflected in the net zero and peatland restoration targets for 2045 and 2030. The policies outlined above should be introduced as soon as possible to ensure that the transition towards net zero is fair and just and does not undermine – but supports – other policy priorities.

¹ E.g., K Stephenson and B Tutko, 'The Role of in Lieu Fee Programs in Wetland/Stream Mitigation Credit Trading: Illustrations from Virginia and Georgia' (2018) 38(6) Wetlands 1211.

Priority should be given to:

- Generating more political and financial support for the Fourth Land Use Strategy to deliver strategic direction to land use change in support of net zero, across cross-sectoral and sectoral policies.
- Designing and delivering an integrated funding framework for wider outcomes/benefits from peatland restoration funding and align other public funding mechanisms, for example, agricultural support.
- Introducing legislation to regulate natural capital markets.

3. What are the expected costs of implementing these policies?

Direct public investment: The Scottish Government has already committed £250 million, over 10 years until 2030, for peatland restoration through the Peatland ACTION grant scheme. It is noted that recent [research](#) commissioned by CXC shows strong regional variation in peatland restoration costs per hectare which should be taken into consideration when funding levels are re-assessed towards the end of this period. Implementing a holistic, benefits-focused approach may require re-evaluating the funding level to ensure it can deliver multiple policy objectives beyond simple hectare targets. At the same time, better integration – and allocation of public funding in such a way that delivers multiple policy objectives – can lead to more resource-efficient implementation, by ensuring that efforts are coordinated, complementary and non-duplicative across relevant sectoral and cross-sectoral policy areas. When done right, a coordinated and integrated approach could lead to the sharing of costs, resources and capacities across departments of Scottish Government.

Governance and regulatory costs: A high-integrity market – one that Government is relying upon to help deliver key environmental targets and objectives – [requires regulation](#), independent monitoring, verification, and enforcement, which must be adequately resourced and publicly funded. Relying on market actors to hold themselves to account risks undermining ecological integrity.

Transaction and capacity-building costs: There are significant ‘hidden’ costs associated with facilitating collaboration and project aggregation, particularly for small- and medium-sized landholders who are at a competitive disadvantage within carbon and nature markets. These costs – for example, for legal advice, building partnerships, and administration – are often not accounted for but they are critical for equitable access. Public funds will be needed to cover these upfront costs to avoid excluding smaller actors.

Opportunity costs for land managers: Undertaking restoration work can affect eligibility for other payments (e.g., agricultural payments), representing opportunity costs that are a potential barrier to action. An integrated funding system needs to be designed to mitigate this.

4. What are the expected benefits of these policies? Please include any wider benefits.

Peatland restoration in Scotland is lagging behind what is needed to meet net zero emissions. The restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands is one of the toughest land-use-change challenges and one requires 1) clarity on how trade-offs (e.g., between production and climate/nature) will be managed through integration at strategic policy level and through alignment of regulatory and financial measures; 2) support for collaborative (and adaptive governance of) projects to enable tenant farmers, crofters, communities and other relevant stakeholders to participate in peatland use decisions, access funding opportunities and benefit from the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

The policies that have been put forward in this response have the potential to provide an answer to these key challenges and thereby accelerate the restoration of agricultural peatlands in a fair and just way. By taking an integrated approach, they will thus deliver a wide range of environmental and social benefits:

- **Climate change mitigation:** Healthy peatlands are the world's largest terrestrial carbon stock, and restoration is critical for delivering Scotland's net-zero target by turning damaged peatlands from a major source of GHG emissions into a carbon sink.

- **Climate change adaptation:** Healthy peatlands provide vital ecosystem functions that can contribute to climate change adaptation, for example, through flood risk management.
- **Biodiversity:** Peatland laws (e.g., the international Ramsar Convention) were originally focused on the biodiversity value of peatlands. In absence of specific nature targets on peatlands (compare EU Nature Restoration Regulation) this value should not be ignored. Peatlands often provide rare habitats (e.g., blanket and raised bogs), with a high diversity of insect species. Biodiversity benefits also often follow from changes in management practices – e.g., lower grazing levels.
- **Water security and quality:** Healthy peatlands store water and contribute to good water quality.
- **Cultural and historic environment:** Healthy peatlands, designated or not, are an important heritage asset. They can preserve important paleoenvironmental records that can also inform and contextualise long-term restoration planning.
- **Community wealth building:** When governed correctly – with community benefit requirements, clear connections to land reform developments, and adequate support for local participation – (peat)land use change can help revitalise rural communities and strengthen local economies, including through new green jobs and more adequate support for traditional practices (e.g., low-intensity grazing).

In addition, it is reiterated that a more integrated approach to peatlands across cross-sectoral and sectoral policies can have important benefits for resource-efficient implementation of policies.

5. What do you think the key challenges would be in delivering these policies?

- **Policy fragmentation and lack of integration:** As detailed above, the fragmented policy space creates conflicting aims and incentives, acting as a major barrier to effective action on the ground.
- **Over-reliance on under-regulated markets:** An increasing emphasis on private markets to deliver public goods is a significant challenge. Without robust governance, this approach risks prioritising economic opportunity over strategic land use, may not deliver genuine ecological outcomes, and can exacerbate social inequalities by favouring large, simple projects over smaller, more complex ones.
- **Concentrated land ownership:** Scotland has an unusually concentrated pattern of rural landownership, which places decision-making power in the hands of relatively few people. This historic and ongoing reality is a fundamental barrier to inclusive and democratic land use change and can hinder the achievement of public objectives.
- **Capacity and access barriers:** Small- and medium-sized landholders, tenants, crofters, and communities often lack the capacity, resources, and upfront funding to support collaboration and engage with complex funding schemes and natural capital markets. This is not only a barrier to achieving a just transition for these land users and stakeholders, but it is a major barrier to unlocking peatland restoration opportunities in large parts of Scotland, for example, on common grazings.
- **Political will:** Implementing policies like robust market regulation and tackling the issue of concentrated land ownership requires significant political courage and long-term commitment.

6. How could these policies support a Just Transition for workers and communities?

A just transition in the LULUCF sector must be intentionally designed into policy. It will not happen automatically, and it requires bolder action and much better integration of policies. It is noted here that in relation to peatlands, the Draft Just Transition Plan for the land use and agricultural sectors only refers to achieving '[h]ectares of restored peatland in Scotland per year' as a measure of success, which is an inadequate indicator for achieving *just processes and outcomes*. Better connections need to be made between the Climate Change Plan, the sectoral Just Transition Plan, the Fourth Land Use Strategy and the Land Reform Bill, to set out a clear course for a just transition for the land use and agricultural sectors.

In this regard, we believe that the policies outlined above can support a just transition by operationalising its three core dimensions:

Procedural justice (fair processes): Co-development is presented as a core element of a fair transition in Scotland, but this must be adequately resourced to address inequities in power and capacity between actors within the land use sector that Scottish Government relies upon to co-develop policies. Legal requirements and governance structures that mandate community involvement at the local level, such as the proposed Land

Management Plans and RLUPs, need to be strengthened and adequately funded, and more research is needed into alternative, adaptive and inclusive governance structures that ensure that those affected by land use change have a genuine say in the decisions that will affect them. Crucially, efforts need to be made to have the voices of future generations represented in current land use decisions due to the longevity or permanency of change (e.g., the average duration of projects under the Peatland Code is 80 years).

Distributive justice (fair outcomes): The transition towards net zero could exacerbate inequities in the land use sector, linked to existing inequalities in access to, ownership of and control over natural resources. An integrated public funding system that is accessible to all landholders, regardless of scale and ownership structures, must ensure that the benefits of the transition are distributed more fairly. By providing public funding for transaction costs and capacity building, the policies would actively address the barriers faced by smaller farmers, tenants, and crofters. A focus on monetary and non-monetary community benefits from natural capital projects, as promoted by the Scottish Land Commission, also holds potential for supporting local economies but is currently largely reliant on efforts at grassroots level, e.g., Community Land Scotland's [Natural Capital Community Partnerships](#).

Restorative justice (addressing past harms): A just transition must scrutinise forward-looking policies that are blind to historic inequalities. By explicitly linking the climate agenda with land reform objectives, and by pushing for the development of inclusive governance structures, new policies can begin to address the legacy of concentrated land ownership and the loss of communal land use in Scotland.

2. AGRICULTURE SECTOR

What are the most important policies needed to achieve the proposed carbon budgets level for 2026-40 in this sector?

The agriculture sector is deeply intertwined with land use, and many of the necessary policies overlap. It is important that this is explicitly recognised in a new Climate Change Plan. It might even be beneficial to have a section that integrates land use, land use change and agriculture, for example, in relation to policy measures that are required to accelerate the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

It is noted that, historically, law and policy, including agricultural payments and loans/grants for (water) management of agricultural land, systematically drove the 'improvement' of agricultural peatlands through drainage and intensification to boost production. Reversing this legacy is a central challenge.

The most important policies are:

- **A new, integrated agricultural support system:** The design of the post-Brexit Scottish Agricultural policy provides a critical opportunity. The overarching objectives of the Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Act 2024 include, among others, to adopt sustainable and regenerative practices, to produce high-quality food, to facilitate on-farm nature restoration, climate mitigation and adaptation and to enable rural communities to thrive. Yet, details are currently lacking on how synergies will be achieved through a new payment scheme. Previous versions of the Agricultural Reform Route Map were explicit on links with peatland restoration funding, but this is less obvious now. A lack of integration of agricultural policy and public funding for peatlands has resulted in conflict, for example, restoration may impact on eligibility of producers to receive agricultural payments.
- **Support for sustainable agricultural management of peatlands:** More research is necessary to understand how multifunctional peat landscapes can be created and, particularly, how sustainable agricultural management of peatlands can be achieved. We are supportive of policy interventions that seek to address the environmental and social aspects of peatland management and restoration in a holistic way. Whilst many environmental goods can be derived from agricultural areas, the delivery of these goods is often inextricably linked to a farmers' primary function and identity as food producers (see this [policy briefing](#) by Proctor *et al*, University of Newcastle) which needs to be considered in the transition towards net zero. Paludiculture in the lowlands, and extensive grazing in the uplands, including with native livestock, could deliver multiple benefits from land, but such (new or traditional) practices require adequate public support (e.g., through a High Nature Value Agriculture scheme).

- **Farm-level capacity building and skills development:** Capacity building and skills development is required to support changes in agricultural practices and ensure that no one is left behind in the transition. Models of delivery could be farmer-led (e.g., on-farm demonstration, training events, farmer-led networks, peer to peer learning) or led by land advisory professional bodies through CPD, training etc. This is where co-design is vital to understand needs, demand and delivery.

When should these policies be introduced, and over what timeframe should they be implemented?

The design of the new agricultural payment schemes is happening now. Delaying action to better integrate agricultural payments with other public funding mechanisms, up the support for multifunctional agricultural systems and build capacity and skills at the farm level, risks locking in unsustainable practices into the 5-year Rural Support Plan (Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Act 2024, s 2).

What are the expected costs of implementing these policies?

Redirection of the agricultural support budget: The largest part of the Scottish agricultural budget is spent on area-based payments with some conditions attached. Better integration of agricultural policy and climate policy (particularly peatland targets) may not necessarily require additional support, although some funding must be redirected to better support integrated management of agricultural peatlands (e.g., see NatureScot's current working on a High Nature Value agricultural scheme which should not solely be viewed from a nature perspective, but should be considered generally for its relevance for managing upland rough grazing areas). Schemes to support the (re)introduction and use of rare and heritage breeds that are well-suited to peat landscapes, and to support collaborative working, for example, stock clubs and advanced joint moorland management, could significantly boost more sustainable management of upland peatlands in Scotland.

Long-term support of appropriate capacity building and skills development programmes: many initiatives for farmer-led mutual-learning and development already exist in Scotland but they are often funded under short (even annual) cycles. Secure and continuous funding is required to ensure lasting impact.

What are the expected benefits of these policies?

The proposed policies have the potential to deliver all of the environmental and social benefits listed for the LULUCF sector, by better supporting the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands. In addition, the proposals can support the economic resilience of the farming sector – in a time where the sector is faced with significant financial uncertainty. Where proposals have been made for better support for extensive grazing in upland (and often remote) peatland areas, the proposals, furthermore, can help keep crofters and farmers on the land, to support diversified, sustainable agricultural businesses. This counters the risk of land being taken out of production for single-objective carbon projects, whilst also recognising the important cultural functions that crofting and farming deliver in many rural communities.

Lastly, by promoting integrated, sustainable use of large areas of Scotland, the policies hold potential of balancing climate and nature benefits with more production-focused demands, including food production.

What do you think the key challenges would be in delivering these policies?

The RESPECT research aims to better understand the motivations and barriers of landholders to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands. We will be able to provide more detailed reflections on key challenges over the next few years. Some challenges that we can identify now:

- **Path dependency and cultural resistance:** Over more than a century, law and policy were geared towards drainage, agricultural improvement and maximising production. Shifting the mindset among farmers and crofters, advisors, and policymakers is still a challenge. Farmers and crofters' primary function and identity is often as food producers, and this must be respected in new policy narratives. -
- **Complexity of designing post-Brexit policies and financial mechanisms in an integrated way:** Since Brexit, Scotland has been preparing, drafting and implementing many different laws and policies on agriculture and environment. This is a huge task and trying to undertake this task in an integrated manner – whilst having the potential of many gains in efficiency – requires coordination and

communication across all levels of Government, which is currently unlikely to be achieved. The Fourth of Land Use Strategy has the potential to play an important role in bringing agricultural policies and other relevant land use-related policies together, but [draft proposals](#) need to be strengthened.

- **Land tenure uncertainties and issues:** There are still significant practical and sometimes legal challenges in relation to undertaking restoration of agricultural peatlands that are under a farming or crofting tenancy or are part of common grazings. There can be practical challenges where decisionmaking power is shared, there can be legal challenges barriers relating to insecure or short-term tenure, or lack of rights to undertake long-term changes to the land under some tenancies, there can also be legal uncertainties in relation to carbon rights. More research and advice are required to overcome these challenges and ensure that no one is excluded from the just transition.

How could these policies support a Just Transition for workers and communities?

The agricultural transition is central to a just transition for rural Scotland.

Procedural justice (fair processes): See LULUCF section (above) on the limitations of co-design.

Distributive justice (fair outcomes): A just transition in agriculture means ensuring that farmers of all scales, types, and tenures can participate and benefit. The policies must be designed to be accessible, providing enhanced support for small farms, new entrants, crofters, and tenants who face the biggest barriers. This prevents a situation where only the most resource-rich landowners can profit from 'nature-based solutions'.

Restorative justice (addressing past harms): The transition offers a chance to correct past policy wrongs. In the past, farmers and crofters were incentivised and sometimes compelled by law to drain peatlands. A just transition needs to recognise this and ensure that they are now supported in restoring peatland ecosystems. A just approach values and builds upon their place-based knowledge of the land. It also involves ensuring that the sector contributes to wider land reform goals, creating a more diverse and equitable pattern of land use and management.

3. GENERAL QUESTIONS

How should the changes required to meet emission reduction targets be funded?

Public finance as the cornerstone: Public funding must remain the primary mechanism for securing public goods from land. It should be used to:

- Provide direct public investment into peatland restoration, with a shift towards outcome-based public funding.
- Fund a new *integrated* agricultural support system, which complements (and does not conflict with) other public funding mechanisms.
- Fund regulation, independent monitoring and enforcement of natural capital projects/standards as well as capacity building and skills development.

A cautious and well-regulated role for private finance: Private investment can complement public funds, but its role must be carefully managed. The current model, which relies on an unregulated voluntary carbon market, poses significant risks to a just transition. A key question that must be addressed is whether using public funds to create, regulate and provide guarantees for a high-integrity private market is the most effective use of those funds, compared to direct public investment in restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands. If private finance is to be encouraged, it must be governed by a framework that:

- Is underpinned by legislation, not just voluntary codes.
- Aligns with public policy goals, including community wealth building and land reform.
- Requires investment to deliver shared benefits for public, private, and community interests, in line with Scotland's Principles for Responsible Investment in Natural Capital.
- Avoids a situation where the public purse underwrites all the financial risk while profits are privatised.

What governance arrangements are needed in the Scottish Government to ensure effective delivery of the CCP?

Our response emphasises the need for better integration of laws and policies relating to agricultural peatlands. This requires genuine cross-departmental collaboration, moving beyond the current fragmentation of laws, policies and institutions.

It may also be necessary to consider new governance arrangements to give much more weight to two key aspects of the transitions towards net zero: 1) strategic direction to policy-making on land use (through the Fourth Land Use Strategy which is currently dependent on cross-sectoral implementation but which could benefit from clearer institutional responsibilities; 2) the just transition framework and sectoral plans (with the advisory function and impact of the Just Transition Commission somewhat limited by its non-statutory status).

There are also opportunities for lower-level governance. We urge for more support for Regional Land Use Partnerships, and for proper evaluation of current Partnerships – their successes and challenges – in light of a potential strengthened role going forward, to support the transition towards net zero at regional level.

Lastly, independent monitoring, verification, and enforcement must be supported by robust governance structures.

How can the Scottish Government ensure transparent monitoring and reporting on progress?

Scottish Government should move beyond 'simple' hectare-based metrics. Current monitoring is heavily focused on the quantitative target of "hectares of restored peatland". While this may be easy to measure, it obscures crucial details about the quality of restoration, the delivery of multiple benefits including climate and biodiversity, and the social impacts at a local level. Where especially the latter may be difficult to measure, it is essential for a just transition that better indicators and measures of success are designed, considered and reviewed to ensure fair processes and outcomes, including at the local level.